

The Impression of Training Entertainment on the Social Expansion of Kindergarten Kids

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ABSTRACT: Undoubtedly the most critical dimension of an individual's personality in terms of society is the social dimension of personality. Social behaviour forms the basis of every person's life. Man is a social being and needs to communicate with others. Many humans' significant needs and flourishing of their talents and abilities can only be entirely fined through interpersonal interaction and social communication—the necessity of social life psychological preparation, social skills, self-confidence and power of the social adjustment. Human growth and development in childhood in terms of social development emotional, cognitive and physical development has characteristics that can make the child vulnerable to mental health.

Social development is the most critical aspect of every person's existence. It is assumed that children can't do without social development and having the necessary skills to perform their duties in social interaction with others. Social growth promotes intellectual growth and other aspects of one's development. In the process, people learn skills, knowledge and adaptation techniques and the possibility of reciprocal relations in continuous interaction their considers social development in the form of the child's mutual adaptation to the social environment and about peers and it is a process that enables the child to understand and predict the behaviour of others, to control their behaviour and regulate their social interactions.

KEYWORDS: Games, Educational games, Social development, Preschool child.

INTRODUCTION

It is essential to pay attention to this point that lack of social skills is a determining factor in increasing children's mental and emotional problems. Pakzadian states that social skills are required for collective life during the socialization process, which is one of the necessities of human life. Human beings are by nature and will be formed in the form of social structures. Social growth is effective in adapting to others. In the future, it will also affect the rate of academic success, career, and social progress; He also states that social behaviour can only be learned through learning and gets used to practice and repetition (Astuti, 2015).

One of the problems of human society today is impaired mobility and weak social relations, which is against the nature of every human being. According to social information processor theory, experiences play an essential role in social development. The game is a collection of physical and mental movements and activities that have caused joy, happiness and communication with others, and it is a means of entertainment. It is also instructive and constructive (Fuchs, 2007).

Maria Montessori is known playing as the big school that kids educated in this school and their physical, mental and social strength growing and be ready for living in a different aspect. Jafari defined playing as a multinational process. Cognitive works research with social skills in preschool kids achieved that these kids have significant improvement in the relationship with a peer group. Jafari indicated in his study that rhythmic movement affects preschool kids social and intellectual growth (Miller et al., 2019). Mahdavinia and Samavati express that education in the first period of life is so important. Educating with playing is one of the most important ways of learning, and they teach children how to overcome problems and solve them (Mahdavinia & Samavati, 2010).

The kid can be familiar with the world around them with playing and achieving there are differences between reality and dream and understand their abilities. At the same time, Emarati and et al., in their research, found that elementary school's playing can cause kids' perceptual and movement growth (Emarati et al. 1012).

One of the different playings is educational playing that gets additional attention. During the exceptional educational playing, the children access the new mental concept and access more and better skills. But skills improvement deals with releasing the inner energy of kids, and the kids learn quickly, which causes social growth, and they can improve their relationship (Wood & Attfield, 2005). They can be more familiar with different colours, shapes and directions and achieve valuable experience without pressure. There are different opinions about the role of playing for being sociable. Some researchers such as Heywood and Garita believe that the participation of kids in group activity and their playing with peers cause their social growth. Also, it claims that social growth with physical activity and playing is weak (Hirsh-Pasek et al., 2015). According to the research and study above, complex human

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relationships in this society and humans passing traditional life to modern life are necessary for social life. This research's goal is to answer this question: Does social playing affect kids' social growth? It needs to pay attention to kids' social property and related factors.

This research can control manipulated elements and experimental works and consider the variables' relationships to be confirmed on the broader community. The research method in the present study is practical. The statistical population is all preschool children in Tehran who were studying in these centres. Multi-stage clusters were selected as the research sample and divided into experimental and control groups. Each group is 99 people.

Thus the first: between all areas of Tehran ministry of education, one place was selected at random, for example, district one of Tehran, then we randomly selected two schools among all preschool centres for girls and boys, for example, a girls school and a boys school were chosen, after selecting schools, two classes were selected from each school. Then the 19 preschoolers from each category were selected. Finally, 90 preschool students were chosen as the research sample. They were randomly tested and controlled in two groups of 99 people.

They tested and controlled both groups by questionnaire (pre-exam); after the pre-test, the experimental group played games like khale Bazi, Gol Bali, Do much ye much, Painting with eyes closed and finding objects. The duration of this experiment was eight weeks. There were two 35 or 45-minute sessions each week.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this research, the Vineland social growth scale four was used as a research tool. The Vineland social growth scale was first developed by a man named Edgar in 1953. Published at Vineland school, it was used for the social growth of US military in world war 1. It was last revised in 1984, and this scale is one of the evolutionary scales (Johnston & Mah, 2008)

This scale measures a person's ability to meet their practical needs and accept responsibility and include a period of the birth of more than 25 years; up to 12 years, for each year, it has a different year but from the age of 12 onwards, between 12 and 15 years old, between 15 and 18-year-old, between 18 and 20 years old, between 20 and 25 years old and up. However, it turns out that it is more efficient at a younger age.

The matter is divided into eight floors: general refusal, refrain from eating, refrain from dressing, self-regulation, occupation, linguistic communication, displacement, and socialization. In each article, the required information isn't obtained through test situations. Instead, it is obtained through an interview with the subjects' parents. The basic of the scale is about a person's ability in daily life and habits. According to the person's score on the scale, we can calculate social age and establish social relationships. The (+) sign on the test score indicates that the child completed the operation and received a positive score. The (-) sign on the test score means that the child has not completed the process and received a grade (Edwards & Liu, 1995).

The (+No) sign on the test score indicates that the child didn't have the opportunity to do it, but the child could do it if the child had the chance. The + sign indicates that the child has successfully performed or performed the desired action and receives a positive score in the test score. A (negative) sign is that the child is showing the desired action and is getting a negative grade. A (NO +) sign indicates that the child has not had the opportunity to do so but can do so if given a chance. If (NO +) is placed between two positive signs, it gets a positive score, and if the top and bottom questions are one positive and the other negative, it gets half a positive score, and if the top and bottom questions are both negative, it gets a score (Germain, 2010).

The sign (F +) indicates that if the problem is solved for the child, she will be able to perform the desired action, in which case she will receive a positive score. The sign (F-) indicates that the child has an irreversible disability, such as amputation of arms or legs, etc., in which case she will not receive a grade. The sign (positive and negative) is a sign that sometimes the child can do an action and other times she can not do that, which is given a positive half score. The validity and validity of the Vineland Scale for 360 people in each age group, including ten males and ten females from birth to 30 years, the standardization and validity or retesting of 123 people, 91 per cent, and the retest interval from one day to 9 It was the moon. In the research of Zadshir et al. (2009), the internal validity of the test was obtained by the internal consistency method through Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.68 (Zadshir et al. 2009).

RESEARCH FINDINGS

This study aimed to investigate the effect of educational games on the social development of preschool children; Data obtained from pre-test and post-test in two experimental and control groups were analyzed using a test (t) and SPS software. In general, the results showed that preschool children who play educational games have more social development.

The results of the t-test showed a significant difference between the rate of social growth of female students who participated in educational games and the rate of social development of female students who did not participate in games. Also, there is a significant difference between the average social growth of male students who participated in educational games and the rate of social growth of male students who did not participate in games. Still, there is a big difference between the impact of educational games on male and female students' social development.

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Table 1: Comparison of the average social growth of girls in the experimental and control groups

Group	Number	Control	The standard deviation	T Calculated	Reliability
Experiment	30	60	2/55		
Control	30	58	1/63	2/8	0/99

As can be seen in Table 1, the difference between the mean social growth calculated 2.89 is larger than the critical t value with a 99% confidence interval and a degree of freedom of 60 (2.67). Therefore, hypothesis 0 is rejected, and the difference between the experimental and control groups in social development is significant.

Table 2: Comparison of the average social development of boys in the experimental and control groups

Group	Number	Control	The standard deviation	T calculated	Reliability
Experiment	30	61	2/75		
Control	30	57/5	3/63	4/21	0/99

As shown in Table 2, the calculated average growth is 4.21 greater than the critical t value with a 99% confidence interval and a degree of freedom of 60 (7.62). Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected, which means that the difference between the experimental and control groups is significant.

Therefore, based on the results, there is a big difference between the average social growth of male students who participated in educational games and the social growth rate of male students who did not participate in games.

Table 3: Comparison of the average social development of girls and boys in the experimental and control groups

Number	Number	Control	The standard deviation	T Calculated	Reliability
Boy experiment	30	60	2/55		
Girl experiment	30	61	2/57	1/42	0/99

According to Table 3, since the calculated coefficient t is 1/42 smaller than the 99% confidence level and 60 (2/62) degrees of freedom, the null hypothesis is not rejected. In other words, there is no significant difference between the social development of the two groups of girls And the boy who participated in the educational games.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Child development is a set of physical, psychological, social, cognitive, emotional and behavioural changes from the fetal period of adolescence. These changes make children unique individuals. In general, human development is an ongoing process in life. Therefore, studies of child development should not forget that the period from embryo to adolescence is not separate from the rest of human development. Social relationships begin at birth and are evident in the daily interactions between the baby's parents and the nurse. Children of social beings are endowed with essential behaviours for initiating and facilitating social interactions (Sigelman & Rider, 2021). Many factors influence social development, including family, school, friends, television, gender and race, socioeconomic status, and motor activities. Is it one of the problems of human society today? Impaired mobility and weakness of social relations are against the nature of every human being. According to the theories of growth and development experts and the research results on the role of movement and motor activities in integrated human development, the correct use of appropriate movement programs with structural features and human psychology, especially in childhood And adolescence, while providing. Physical and mental health prepares a person for life in a social environment. Among these motor skills for children and adolescents is played (Berns, 2015).

One of the types of games is educational games. A game that is a multidimensional process that serves the development and growth of the child and can be a way to drain the child's inner energies and pave the way for his learning; And lead to the child's social

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development and improvement of communication skills. During games, especially educational games, children will gain access to new mental concepts and acquire more and better skills. They play with the colours of May. Please get to know different shapes and directions and bring valuable experiences; During the game, he learns the material to be understood without pressure and with desire (Lester & Russell, 2010).

Accordingly, the present study was conducted to investigate the effect of educational games on the social development of preschool children. Examination of the scores obtained from the Vineland Social Development Test in the two experimental and control groups and comparing them shows an essential education on the social development of male and female preschool students. Ceylan et al. (2015) has done a lot of research on play therapy. By observing and comparing children's play in the Yale Clinic, he identified cases of behavioural and emotional differences between children and their adherence to parental education. Children who are unable to play and cannot play like other children their peers are among those who use the term play therapy. In a 2010 study, Stupp reported a significant correlation between motor activity and children's academic achievement (Stupp et al. 2010).

Bratton et al. (2015) investigated the impact of play therapy on the social development of children 4-6 years old with delayed social development in the infant Ameneh who, based on the calculation of the Vineland Social Maturity Scale for children in the experimental and control groups, showed that the average difference The social age of the children in the control group with the experimental group was not significant before play therapy. If this difference between the mean in the control and test groups after play therapy is substantial. That is, play therapy has increased the social age of children in the experimental group. According to the above research results, which is consistent with the results of the present study and confirms the research results, it can be said that educational games influence the social development of preschool children and cause their social development.

According to the present study results, it is suggested that the current research being conducted at the provincial and national levels provide a clear picture of the use of educational games in social skills and development. Since this research is dedicated to preschool, it is suggested that using educational games in learning different subjects and the skills and social development of elementary students should be examined in other crude grades. Due to the interaction and constructive interaction of school and community and its essential role in students' social upbringing, further research on the socio-cultural environment of schools and methods of adaptation – content, goals and strategies of school social education with community realities And be more complete. In this study, the effect of educational games on social development was investigated. Educational games can be placed on other children's skills, including physical, social, mental, creative and other skills.

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